

Promoting Intersectional Fairness through Knowledge Distillation - Supplementary Materials

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1 Datasets

For our experiment, we choose five widely used datasets to evaluate our framework.

1. **Adult-Income:** We use the Adult-Income dataset from UCI repository contains 48,842 instances of census records with demographic and employment related features. The binary prediction task is whether an individuals annual income exceeds 50,000 USD. For our experiment, we use race and gender as sensitive attributes (binary).
2. **COMPAS:** The COMPAS [1] dataset consists of criminal history, demographic attributes, and risk scores for over 7,000 individuals asses for recidivism. The target is a binary outcome indicating re-offense within two years. We consider gender and race as sensitive attributes.
3. **German Credit Dataset:** This dataset is for evaluating financial risk assessment that contains 1000 instances with 20 attributes capturing applicant characteristics. This has sensitive attribute like age, employment status.
4. **MIMIC-III:** MIMIC-III [2] is a credentialed-access clinical dataset consists over 60,000 ICU admissions, with records including vital signs, medications, and diagnostic codes. In our setup, the prediction task involves categorizing patients based on their ICU length of stay into four ordinal classes: less than 3 days, 3–7 days, 7–14 days, and more than 14 days. We treat gender and ethnicity as sensitive attributes. Ethnicity is categorized into five groups, yielding a total of 10 intersectional subgroups when combined with binary gender. This setup allows us to evaluate fairness in a multi-class classification setting and assess performance across non-binary and intersectional sensitive attributes in a high-stakes healthcare context.
5. **MIMIC-IV:** MIMIC-IV [3] is also a credentialed access clinical dataset containing 94,444 unique ICU admission. Like the MIMIC-III dataset we use the length of stays as target attribute.

2 Computational Efficiency

In Table 1, we show that our student model is taking less parameters in training than the teacher model but with fairness constraint, we achieve better performance in the fairness criteria of minimum of 44% improvement in the Demographic Parity Ratio (DPR) GAP.

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3 Hyperparameters for Reproducibility

The hyperparameters necessary to reproduce the results are shown in Table 5, while the algorithm is detailed in Algorithm 1.

The code can be found at <https://github.com/fahim-sikder/FairX>

4 More Results

We present the result of German dataset in Table 2. Table 3 and 4 present the performance of our model on MIMIC-III and MIMIC-IV data including the FPR for subgroups¹. Also we present the overall architecture of our proposed method in Figure 1.

References

- [1] J. Angwin, J. Larson, S. Mattu, and L. Kirchner. Machine bias: There's software used across the country to predict future criminals. and it's biased against blacks. <https://www.propublica.org/article/machine-bias-risk-assessments-in-criminal-sentencing>, 2016. [Online; accessed 12-Aug-2024].
- [2] A. E. Johnson, T. J. Pollard, L. Shen, L.-w. H. Lehman, M. Feng, M. Ghassemi, B. Moody, P. Szolovits, L. Anthony Celi, and R. G. Mark. MIMIC-iii, a freely accessible critical care database. *Scientific data*, 3(1): 1–9, 2016.
- [3] A. E. Johnson, L. Bulgarelli, L. Shen, A. Gayles, A. Shammout, S. Horng, T. J. Pollard, S. Hao, B. Moody, B. Gow, et al. MIMIC-iv, a freely accessible electronic health record dataset. *Scientific data*, 10(1): 1, 2023.

¹ The Ethnicity label used here is derived directly from the dataset

Figure 1. Overall architecture of our proposed model

Table 1. Computational Efficiency of using Student model Compared to Teacher Model

Dataset	Teacher Parameters	Student Parameters	Compression Ratio	DPR GAP Improvement (%)
Adult-Income	37952	10624	3.57x	77
COMPAS	76736	30016	2.56x	48
German	32832	8064	4.07x	58
MIMIC-III	27712	5504	5.03x	75
MIMIC-IV	32192	7744	4.16x	44

Table 2. Evaluation of German Credit Dataset (bold indicates best result, \uparrow indicates higher as better, \downarrow indicates lower as better)

Gender	Age-group	FLDGs	FairDisco	FSNS	Baseline	Ours
Subgroup FPRs (\downarrow)						
Female	Young	0.33	0.25	0.25	0.58	0.08
Female	Old	0.29	0.33	0.10	0.23	0.11
Male	Young	0.00	0.28	0.16	0.71	0.00
Male	Old	0.25	0.23	0.12	0.26	0.03
Overall Metrics						
Accuracy (\uparrow)		0.63	0.61	0.76	0.57	0.69
DPR Gender (\uparrow)		0.89	0.90	0.69	0.63	0.65
DPR Race (\uparrow)		0.75	0.69	0.78	0.76	0.79

Table 3. Evaluation of MIMIC-III Dataset (bold indicates best result, \uparrow indicates higher as better, \downarrow indicates lower as better)

Gender	Ethnicity	Ours
Subgroup FPRs (\downarrow)		
Female	White	0.0623
Female	Black	0.0524
Female	Hispanic	0.0370
Female	Asian	0.0577
Female	Other	0.0419
Male	White	0.0538
Male	Black	0.0591
Male	Hispanic	0.0446
Male	Asian	0.0435
Male	Other	0.0822
Overall Metrics		
Accuracy (\uparrow)		0.92
DPR Gender (\uparrow)		0.98
DPR Ethnicity (\uparrow)		0.70

Table 4. Evaluation of MIMIC-IV Dataset (bold indicates best result, \uparrow indicates higher as better, \downarrow indicates lower as better)

Gender	Ethnicity	Ours
Subgroup FPRs (\downarrow)		
Female	White	0.0297
Female	Black	0.0237
Female	Hispanic	0.0233
Female	Asian	0.0205
Female	Other	0.0230
Female	American_Indian	0.000
Female	Portuguese	0.0303
Female	UNKNOWN	0.0202
Male	White	0.0278
Male	Black	0.0130
Male	Hispanic	0.0186
Male	Asian	0.0196
Male	Other	0.0165
Male	American_Indian	0.0000
Male	Portuguese	0.0238
Male	UNKNOWN	0.0214
Overall Metrics		
Accuracy (\uparrow)		0.97
DPR Gender (\uparrow)		0.97
DPR Ethnicity (\uparrow)		0.71

Table 5. Optimal Hyperparameters

Parameters	Datasets				
	Adult-Income	COMPAS	German	MIMIC-III	MIMIC-IV
α_1	0.6	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.3
α_2	0.06	0.05	0.03	0.05	0.05
α_3	0.15	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.1
α_4	7	10	4	9	9
α_5	2	3	3	4	4
α_6	2	3	2	3	3
α_7	5	2	5	2	2
Learning rate	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
Optimizer	Adam	Adam	Adam	Adam	Adam
Epoch	400	400	400	400	400
T.E - Hidden Layer 1	Features	Features	Features	Features	Features
T.E - Hidden Layer 2	128	128	128	128	128
T.E - Hidden Layer 3	64	64	64	64	64
S.E - Hidden Layer 1	Features	Features	Features	Features	Features
S.E - Hidden Layer 2	64	64	64	64	64

Algorithm 1 Algorithm of our Framework

Require: Dataset $\mathcal{D} = \{(x_i, y_i, s_i)\}_{i=1}^N$, learning rate η , epochs $T_{\text{teach}}, T_{\text{distill}}$, weights $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4, \alpha_5, \alpha_6, \alpha_7$

Ensure: Fair student encoder f_s and classifier g_s

- 1: **Phase 1: Train teacher without fairness**
- 2: Initialize teacher encoder f_t and classifier g_t
- 3: **for** $e = 1$ to T_{teach} **do**
- 4: **for** each mini-batch $(X, Y, S) \subset \mathcal{D}$ **do**
- 5: $Z_t \leftarrow f_t(X)$
- 6: $\mathcal{L}_{\text{cls}} \leftarrow \text{CE}(g_t(Z_t), Y)$
- 7: Update f_t, g_t by $\nabla \mathcal{L}_{\text{cls}}$
- 8: **end for**
- 9: **end for**
- 10: **Phase 2: Distill with fairness constraints**
- 11: Initialize student encoder f_s , student classifier g_s , and predictor d
- 12: **for** $e = 1$ to T_{distill} **do**
- 13: **for** each mini-batch $(X, Y, S) \subset \mathcal{D}$ **do**
- 14: $Z_t \leftarrow f_t(X), L_t \leftarrow g_t(Z_t)$
- 15: $Z_s \leftarrow f_s(X), L_s \leftarrow g_s(Z_s)$
- 16: $\mathcal{L}_{\text{cls}} \leftarrow \text{WCE}(L_s, Y)$
- 17: $\mathcal{L}_{\text{repr}} \leftarrow \|\text{Norm}(Z_s) - \text{Norm}(Z_t)\|^2$
- 18: $\mathcal{L}_{\text{pred}} \leftarrow \text{KL}(\text{softmax}(L_s), \text{softmax}(L_t))$
- 19: **for** $k = 1$ to K **do**
- 20: $\mathcal{L}_{\text{adv}} \leftarrow \|d(Z_s) - S\|^2$
- 21: Update d by $\nabla \mathcal{L}_{\text{adv}}$
- 22: **end for**
- 23: $\mathcal{L}_{\text{fair}} \leftarrow \text{FPR_Loss}(Z_s, Y, S, g_s, \alpha_4, \alpha_5, \alpha_6)$
- 24: $\mathcal{L}_{\text{adv_enc}} \leftarrow -\|P(Z_s) - S\|^2$
- 25: $\mathcal{L} \leftarrow \alpha_1 \mathcal{L}_{\text{cls}} + \alpha_2 \mathcal{L}_{\text{repr}} + \alpha_3 \mathcal{L}_{\text{pred}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{fair}} + \alpha_7 \mathcal{L}_{\text{adv_enc}}$
- 26: Update f_s, g_s by $\nabla \mathcal{L}$
- 27: **end for**
- 28: **end for**
- 29: **return** f_s, g_s
